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GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

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Analysis of Structural Geology based on Sattelite Image and Geological Mapping on Binuang Area, Tapin Region, South Kalimantan

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ABSTRACT

Study area lies on Binuang, Binuang District, Tapin Regency, South Kalimantan Province. In geographically this area lies on 115° 6' 28" E - 115° 11' 28" E dan 3° 13' 10" S - 3° 8' 10" S and include in topographic map sheet no. 1712-63 (Binuang) which published by Bakorsurtanal.

This area has a complex conditional of structural geology based on satellite image feature and supported by geological field mapping. There are five major faults and one fold could be identified clearly on this study area, which are Normal Fault (Batangbanyu), Thrust Fault (Gunung Batu-1), Strike-slip fault (Gunungulin, Gunung Batu-1, Bumbun, and Hantan) and Batangkayu syncline. Mechanism of forming faults are affected by Meratus Range movement on east. Starting on paleogen, extensional stress more extensive which resulting Batangbanyu normal fault. Then, at Neogene, compressional stress more extensive working in this area which resulting synthetic fault (Gunungulin and Gunungbatu-2) with NS – SE direction and antithetic fault (Bumbun and Hantan) at opposite direction. Another fault are formed perpendicular with major fault which are Gunung batu-1 thrust fault and Batangkayu syncline.

Keywords : Binuang, Faults, Meartus, Compressional, Extensional.

INTRODUCTION

Binuang area geologically aged from cretaceous until tertiary. But from the literature, the detail of geological structure still not much expose yet. So it's still need further research to explain the area in detail. This purpose of this research is knowing the dynamic of structural geology and analyze possibility tectonic that affected on the area.

GEOLOGY REGIONAL

Research area are include on Barito Basin which are assymetrical basin which is located in the Southeast Sundaland. On the northern part of the basin, There is Adang Fault that separates the basin with Kutai Basin. In the eastern area, meratus mountain separated this basin with Asem-asem Basin (Figure 1).

Structural geology on Barito basin controlled by two major tectonics, which are:

1. Meratus Mountain
2. Adang Fault (Sinistral with WNW – ESE direction, as a transform fault affected from Makassar strait rifting, Kusuma & Darin, 1989).

There are three Tectonic period time that affected the basin, that is on:

1. Paleogen (Eosen),
2. Middle Miosen
3. Plio-Plistosen

According to Kusuma & Darin (1989), rifting that resulting number of graben trending NW - SE formed at this age. This structure interpreted as a pull-apart basin bounded by sinistral fault syn-depositional landscape. This structure became the basement of Tertiary sediments in this basin. The feature of full graben are interoreded by gravity data, well data and seismic maps.

Inversion graben are not too obvious in this basin. In the northern part of the basin, the structure of the Eocene - Oligocene tectonics covered by tectonic Plio-Pleistocene. In the southern part of the Barito basin, there are not visible clearly an inversion of this graben.

According Sikumbang (1986, in Kusuma & Darin 1989), the results of rifting basin was formed by a horizontal trending sinistral wrenching along Meratus path followed by oblique continental collisions. In the Late Cretaceous, the sinistral wrenching occur meratus produce pull -apart basin trending NW- SE bounded by sinistral wrench fault syn - depositional. At the beginning of the Eocene epoch, tectonic in southern Kalimantan dominated wrench divergent styles, it is likely due to the relative movement of the Australian plate. Tensional stress is causing basin NW- SE raised and followed by subsidence and sedimentation process that continues until the Late Miocene. Then, at Miocene, Meratus mountains uplifted. This looked on layer sediments on the Barito basin in the western part of the relatively flat and increasingly steep on eastward. Uplifting Meratus also characterized by thickening Warukin Formation toward the mountains. This uplift continues or become active again at Plio - Pleistocene period, when compression seem to be more dominant and lead to the presence of reverse fault configuration.

Plio - Pleistocene structure are strong folds trending N-S, which involves the basement and exposed partially or entirely into the pre - tertiary ridge. The folds formed arc oblique direction relative to the main zone of deformed mountains

Based on Kusuma & Darin (1989), this structure are converging wrench patterns. Wrench tectonic model also takes effect of compression structures in southern areas that expected to be a local tensile force.

Satyana & Silitonga (1993) interpreted the folds that is associated with the occurrence of Plio – Plistocene fault, which involves only a few tectonic in any part of the west and a lot on the east. Tectonics on the western part not involve pre - Tertiary basement. While on tectonics in the eastern involve prateritary basement, resulting fault rift at Eocene.

According to Mason (1993) tectonic Plio- Plisto not produce folds, because the fold are the result of the earlier tectonic (Eocene - Oligocene and Miocene), which is characterized by the presence of unconformity.

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Figure 1. Location of study area overlay with tectonic in Barito Basin (.Kusuma & Darin, 1989)

Plio - Pleistocene tectonic only produces faults, which are:

1. Thrust fault with dip towards the west
These faults trending N- S , with a convex shape towards the west. This fault formed by assumed by the uplift the Central Kalimantan craton.
2. Thrust Fault with dip towards the east
This fault also trending N- S with a convex shape towards the east. This fault was caused by the increasing Meratus mountains.
3. Strike-Slip Fault
Strike slip Fault cutting the existed reverse fault and became the last structures formed. These faults are common in the northern part of the basin and cutting the reverse fault which has a dip towards the east and the west. This fault interpreted as the result of force detachment fault due to reverse fault that face each other.

Faulting and imbricating on Plio-Pleistocene structure generally affected by compression related to meratus uplifting and followed by faulting on western part and also caused by uplifting the Sunda continen to the western part. Opening phase South Makassar Basin at Miocene pushing microplate Paternosfer to the west, and making tangential force to the Meratus which resulting uplifting and thrust fault on Barito Basin.

Widening the Makasar strait on nothern part not followed on the southern part, resulting uplift imbrication belt and large thrust fault at northern part of Barito basin, but at southern only a local thrust fault. Large Thrust fold belt at the north Tanjung related with Adang Sinistral Fault.

DATA

Data used for this research are satellite image and field data which are the stike dip, slicken side, 220 joint data from nine spot staion found on the field.

METHOD AND ANALYSIS

Analysis and method that used for reconstructing structure on this area are by picking lineament from satellite image and measuring fault data and joint data in the field. Then, analyze it by using streographic for defining major stress fault.

STRUCTURAL INTERPRETATION

At this stage, interpretation made from Landsat satellite image by combining band 4,5,7 with digital elevation model (Figure 2). From the analysis of Landsat imagery in the research area shows a number of lineament that interpret as a geological structure. Straightness can be interpreted are river lineament, lithological boundaries, layering rock, fold axis, joint, and faults.

Lineament interpretation of satellite imagery with manual-visual produce 149 straightness with a length ranging from 416 to 2666 m. Straightness of the length frequency graph (Figure 2, right) shows the maximum value in the range of 1100 to 1200m. Measurement directions lineament interpretation (Figure 3) shows some dominant lineament orientation which are as northeast-southwest, the east-west and northwest-southeast.

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Figure 2. Interpretation fault lineament from satellite image and graphic of total length of lineament frequency.

Figure 3. Rose diagram lineament result from satellite image interpretation.

FOLD STRUCTURES

Based on strike reconstruction result, there are one major fold that is Batangkayu Sinklin as a reconstruction strike/dip result, supported by lineaments from satellite image and topography at NE – SW direction, located on the middle research area. From interpretation resulting fold geometry and kinematics as follow:

1. NW limb N 202° E / 25°
2. SE limb N 19° E / 68°
3. Interlimb angle 82°
4. Fold axis plane N 200° E / 72°
5. Trend 20°
6. Plunge 1°

Based on fold classification according to Fleuty, 1964, this is open horizontal fold.

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Figure 4. Stereographic analysis of Batangkayu syncline.

Figure 5. Fold limb of Sungai Hatungun syncline.

FAULT STRUCTURES

Batangbanyu Fault

This fault has W-E orientation at souther part of study area. Based on analysis of slicken side data, that this fault showing relatively normal movement. It was indicated by :

1. Lineament on landsat image which showing W-E orientation. On image that can be observed from the

textural different between nrthern and southern part of the lineament.

2. Analysis of slicken side data (Figure 6) menunjukkan cermin sesar with direction dengan N 50° E/59°, pitch 80 SE, normal movement and stress system $\sigma_1 = N 233^\circ E / 17^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 342^\circ E / 47^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 129^\circ E / 38^\circ$.

Figure 6. Stereographic analysis of Batangbanyu Fault.

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This fault was cut the Basalt Lava Unit and formed as the effect of NE-SW compression tectonic at Paleosen period.

Gunungulin Fault

This fault extend with NW-SE direction. Located at southeastern part of study area that indicated from :

- 1. Lineament of landsat image with NW-SE Orientation.
- 2. Slickenside data (Figure 7) showing direction N 90° E / 35°, pitch 65° SE and N 100° E / 85, pitch 73° SE,

sinistral. Stress system of this fault are $\sigma_1 = N 65^\circ E / 59^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 284^\circ E / 24^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 186^\circ E / 18^\circ$.

- 3. Analysis group of joint data at Gunungulin Fault (Figure 8) showing maximum NW-SE direction with major fault plane N 124° E/ 39°, pitch 39 SE, sinistral. Stress system of this jaont are $\sigma_1 = N 78^\circ E / 42^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 200^\circ E / 45^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 178^\circ E / 12^\circ$.
- 4. Analysis of shear fracture data and slciken side (Figure 9) Resulting $\sigma_1 = N 74^\circ E / 41^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 335^\circ E / 9^\circ$, dan $\sigma_3 = N 235^\circ E / 47^\circ$.

Figure 7. Stereographic Analysis of Gunungulin Fault.

Figure 8. Stereographic and rose diagram analysis of fracture data along Gunungulin Fault.

Figure 9. Analysis group of fracture and slicken side along Gunungulin fault.

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This fault intersects Late Oligocene limestone unit as the result of northeast-southwest compression and estimated this fault was formed in the Middle Miocene period until Pliocene-Pleistocene.

Bumbun Fault

This fault extends from NE – SW. Located in the northwestern part of the study area. Indication of this fault are:

1. The alignment on the satellite image oriented northeast-southwest.

2. Slicken side at field (Figure 10) showing direction N 32° E / 76°, pitch 20 SW, dextral. Resulting stress system $\sigma_1 = N 227^\circ E/6^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 321^\circ E/31^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 127^\circ E/58^\circ$.
3. Stereographic analysis of joint data (Figure 11) Showing Maximum direction NE-SW. The result are $\sigma_1 = N 182^\circ E/19^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 294^\circ E/48^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 78^\circ E/37^\circ$.
4. Analysis of major joint and slicken side data (Figure 12) the result are $\sigma_1 = N 219^\circ E/ 49^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 128^\circ E/ 1^\circ$, dan $\sigma_3 = N 37^\circ E/ 41^\circ$.

Figure 10. Stereographic analysis of Slicken side of Bumbun Fault.

Figure 11. Analysis stereographic and rose diagram of fracture data along Bumbun Fault.

Figure 12. Stereographic Analysis major fracture data and slicken side near Bumbun Fault.

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Figure 13. Offset data with slicken side of Bumbun Fault showing dextral movement.

This fault direction relatively NE-SW, and perpendicular and intersect with Gunungulin Fault that trending NW-SE, and estimated that this fault is synthetic with the Gunungulin fault by cutting tuff breccia unit and formed by NE-SW compression and formed in the Middle Miocene tectonic period until Plio-Pleistocene.

Gunungbatu-2 Fault

This fault extends at NW-SE direction. Located in the western part of the study area. Indication of this fault are:

1. Lineament on satellite images show the northwest-southeast orientation.
2. Analysis of group of fracture along this fault lineament (Figure 13) showing NE-SW direction with strike dip data N 302° E/ 71°, pitch 45 SW, sinistral. And the result are $\sigma_1 = N 263^\circ E/ 46^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 104^\circ E/ 42^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 5^\circ E/ 10^\circ$.

Figure 14. Analysis group o fracture near Gunungbatu 2 fault.

This fault cut tuf breccia unit and formed as NE-SW compression, tectonic period interpreted formed at Middle Miocene until Pliocene-Pleistocene.

Gunungbatu-1 Fault

This fault extends to the northeast-southwest direction. Located at the center of the study area. Slickenside data are not found in this site, but is is interpret from analysisi of fracture data. This fault cut all tertiary rocks in the study area. Indication that this fault are:

1. Lineament on satellite images that show differences in texture and color which trending NE-SW.
2. The emergence of old Cretaceous litology into the surface and cut Oligocene rock unit.
3. Analysis group of fracture in all site location near the lineament of this fault (Figure 14) Showing direction NE-SW with strike dip data N 195° E/ 84°, pitch 67° SW. The result are $\sigma_1 = N 245^\circ E/ 53^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 12^\circ E/ 25^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 115^\circ E/ 26^\circ$.

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Gambar15. Analysis stereographic and rose diagram of fracture data along Gunungbatu Fault.

This fault cuts the limestone unit and uplift tuff breccia unit and Late Cretaceous lava basalt to the surface. Fault was formed by NE-SW compression and predicted to form in the Middle Miocene tectonic period until Pliocene-Pleistocene.

Hantan Fault

This fault trending W-E direction. Located on northeastern part of study area and relatively parallel with hantan river. Indication of this fault are:

1. Lineament on satellite images that show straightness oriented east-west in the eastern of study area .
2. Slicken side data (Figure15) showing N 270° E / 55°, pitch 35° NE, relatively dextral. The result are $\sigma_1 = N$

155° E / 39°, $\sigma_2 = N 267^\circ E / 25^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 21^\circ E / 41^\circ$.

3. Analysis fracture on field (Figure 16) trending E-W. The result are $\sigma_1 = N 115^\circ E / 54^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 303^\circ E / 35^\circ$, dan $\sigma_3 = N 210^\circ E / 4^\circ$.
4. Analysis of major fracture and slicken side (Figure 17) resulting $\sigma_1 = N 118^\circ E / 49^\circ$, $\sigma_2 = N 213^\circ E / 4^\circ$, and $\sigma_3 = N 307^\circ E / 41^\circ$.

This fault cut breccia tuff unit and formed by the NW-SE compression interpret to form in the period of Middle Miocene tectonic to Pliocene-Pleistocene.

Gambar 16. Analysis of slicken side Hantan Fault.

Figure 17. Analysis stereographic and rose diagram of fracture data along Hantan Fault.

Figure 18. Analysis Major fracture plane and slicken side along Hantan fault.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on field data, satellite image, and topography interpretation, tectonics on reserach area began on Cretaceous until quarter period. That based on the emerge of cretaceous rock and recent sediment on the field.

It's estimated after late cretaceous – Paleosen, extensional force happen in NE-SW direction, resulting normal fault W-E direction. This normal fault are became place for sediment to accumulate. Generally extensional force persisted since Eocene to Early Miocene, it is characterized by the presence of sedimentary Eocene to Early Miocene.

Middle Miocene tectonics at first stage is not clearly visible, which predicted from the absence of sediments younger than the Early Miocene sediments. And It is estimated at this time, there was a compressional force trending northwest-southeast that resulting Batangkayu syncline. Compressional relatively weak, showing only gentle fold.

Entering Tectonic at Pliocene – Pleistocene compresional with NW-SE direction is getting stronger and resulting many faults in this area such as Gunungulin Fault, Gunungbatu Fault, Hantan Fault, Bumbun Fault, and sesar Gunungbatu 2.

Tectonic framework of the research areas included in the Barito basin tectonics which located in the southeastern part Sundaland.

Tectonic basin is highly influenced by mountain ranges and fault Meratus Adang.

Barito basin formation begins with rifting at Paleogene, and produced number of horst and graben trending northwest-southeast. At Middle Miocene, mountain Meratus began to rise as a result of collisions in eastern Sulawesi. The compressional force becomes denser resulting collision and uplift, and also inverse the normal faults in the basin. Then, compression force add due to the interaction of the Indo-Australian plate and the Pacific.

At Neogen, SW-NE compression trending north-east forcing the South Kalimantan. This compression maks all normal faults reactivated and becoming sinistral wrench fault. This strike slip movement trigger folds and reverse fault.

If we compared with the regional tectonic Barito basin, it can be concluded that the geological structure in the study area is divided into two, namely the Paleogene and Neogene period. Period of tectonic Paleogene age is an extensional tectonic style, thus forming a normal fault trending NW-SE. While at Neogene tectonic period, the study area is controlled by the horizontal sinistral wrench fault of wrench Meratus zone. Based on the Riedel Shear model (Figure 19), Gunungulin Fault , Gunungbatu-2 faults, interpreted as synthetic faults, because it has the same direction and movement of the major fault (sinistral). Thrust Fault and fods are caused also by this major fault. And dextral formed fault interpreted as antithetic fault.

Figure 19. Applied Riedel shear model for neogen tectonic on study area.

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Figure 20. Geological Structure map with stereographical analysis on study area.

CONCLUSION

1. Based on analysis field data and interpretation of satellite images shows three dominant directions, which are: northeast-southwest, east-west and northwest-southeast. This direction is estimated as the direction of the main geological structure of the study area.
2. Tectonics in this study area are related with Barito basin tectonic which affected by forming of meratus mountain and andang fault. Began at Paleogen, extensional force occurs relatively northeast-southwest, causing Batangbanyu fault formed as a normal fault. Then, at Neogene compressional force occur trending northwest-southeast resulting Meratus mountains rising, and causing sinistral wrench fault resulting reverse fault and folds. Gunungulin fault and Gunungbatu2 fault, as a synthetic fault, the trending northwest-southeast, different with Bumbun fault and Hantan fault, as an antithetic fault that oppose direction with synthetic faults. and also resulting Gunungbatu thrust Fault and Batangkayu syncline which perpendicular to the compression forces.

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